

Supplementary Material 1

1. Boundary conditions

The following boundary conditions are common to all scenarios that have been simulated.

- *Demographic module*: Model default parameters adopted
- *Stressor module*: Reduction of target greenhouse gas emission intensity of 30% by 2100 for all types of greenhouse gases (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, SF₆, HFC, PFC).
- *Land module*: Constant land intensities, default model values for remaining land parameters, land scarcity factor deactivated, which allows output to grow independent from the availability of demanded land types.
- *Labor module*: Default model values for annual working hours (2080 hours) and maximum participation rate (95%).
- *Economic module*: constant capital intensities; target consumption vector for public consumption, private consumption and GFCF: complete substitution of fossil and nuclear electricity by solar, wind and hydropower by 2100; target consumption vector corresponding to households with low consumption levels: share of food sector reduced by 20%; 10% shifted to service sector, 10% shifted to industry sector; A-Matrix: complete substitution of fossil and nuclear electricity by solar, wind and hydropower by 2100; energy efficiency improvements in industrial processes by 2100: 5% in all processes across all sectors; moderate electrification and efficiency gains in the fossil resources, bioenergy, electricity, industry, manufacturing, services, chemical, transport and renewable waste sectors; convergence in consumption

For convergence processes, the relative consumption multipliers have been specified to decrease from 46:1 to 8:1 (R20C to P30P class) in 2100 for low consumption growth scenarios, to 6:1 for medium consumption growth scenarios, and to 6.5:1 for high consumption growth scenarios.

2. Land demand and disposable land

Suppl. Figure 1 and Suppl. Figure 2 show the evolution of the ratio between the amount of land required for economic production under constant land intensities (i.e. at the level of 2019) and the maximum land supply that depends on the size of habitable land, which is reduced by climate change impacts. Results are shown for 12 of the 120 simulated

scenarios.

Suppl. Figure 1: Ratio between land demanded for economic production and maximum land supply during the simulations for six scenarios with low labor productivity or low consumption growth (12133, 12222, 12311, 21133, 21222, 21311).

Suppl. Figure 2: Ratio between land demanded for economic production and maximum land supply during the simulations for six scenarios with high labor productivity or high consumption growth (23133, 23222, 23311, 32133, 32222, 32311).